

The Impact Of Determents For Adoption Of E-Wallet Payment System Regarding Paytm

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Abstract

The digital wallet system incorporates three typical electronic payment instruments: cash, check, & card. The primary function of electronic payment is to move money from payer to payee. The current period is approaching a new phase in payment system. In today's bustling world, people don't have time to stop and rest, so how can they accomplish their daily tasks like "recharging their phones, paying their power bill, insurance, or shopping" etc. As a result, digital wallet applications have been launched to alleviate people's concerns. Individuals are increasingly adopting digital wallets on their cell phones. Working on the Digital wallet system is quite simple; we just register an account on Digital wallet & retain our money digitally in our e-wallet. It is also useful for online transactions, purchases, and so forth. Moreover, it may be used for online purchasing. As a result, it has evolved into both a payment platform & a marketplace over time. The current study is based on primary & secondary data, which was gathered through a variety of random sampling, books, business magazines, journals, newspapers, research studies, internet, web sites, & so on. This will highlight users' usage of digital wallets, with a focus on Paytm in the Meerut region. Paytm is becoming more popular in today's corporate sector, as are mobile phones. Individuals use mobile devices to access numerous capabilities wherever they are and whenever they need them. Moreover, Paytm is playing an important role by allowing customers to make online payments. Paytm has also provided ability of recharging & purchasing from anywhere & at any time by utilizing a secure online wallet known as Paytm cash.

The present analysis is undertaken with the purpose of investigating a consumer adoption of digital wallet special reference to Paytm in Meerut region. The study also tries to explore usage, risk, preferences and benefits towards adoption of digital wallet in Meerut Region. The findings of study support that adoption of digital wallet has a significant relation with preference and awareness. Respondents prefer non-banking digital wallets over banking wallets. Respondents are aware about maximum number of wallets operating in India. Again, the data of awareness level indicated those non-banking digital wallets are very much known as compared to banking wallets. Awareness and demographic variables (gender, age, income, qualification and occupation) when analyzed resulted that except occupation, in case of age, gender, qualification and income alternate hypothesis is accepted which says that there is a significant difference b/w demographic profile of respondents & awareness level.

Keywords

E-Wallet, Payment System, Digital Wallet, Demonetization, Paytm.

Introduction

Making payments (electricity, water, taxes, etc.), shopping online, buying cinema tickets, reserving train & aeroplane seats, & many other transactions are made easier with a digital wallet. The usage of a digital wallet is secure because it eliminates the need to carry real money for payment; instead, payment is made electronically, which promotes cashless transactions. One advantage of a digital wallet is that a person does not need to carry currency all the time; payments or money may be transmitted from any spot to the appropriate folks anywhere on the globe. Digital wallets may also be used to pay fees and conduct other financial transactions from anywhere and at any time, saving a significant amount of time and effort. Digital wallets offer both advantages and downsides. For example, they may be hacked by anybody, and passwords might be misplaced, leading in losses. Accessing the digital wallet necessitates a connection to an electronic device for interactions, which is not accessible to everyone. A data connection is also necessary, which is not always feasible for low-income individuals. Thus, while a digital wallet is something that everybody can use and that makes life simpler, it cannot always be so advantageous because it has some limits. Since the demonetization, the use of e-wallets has skyrocketed as individuals transition to a cashless economy, allowing them to utilize this gadget or service anywhere, at any time. E-wallets are excelling in financial services because they eliminate the need for individuals to visit banks for transactions.

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appropriate folks anywhere on the globe. Digital wallets may also be used to pay fees and conduct other financial transactions from anywhere and at any time, saving a significant amount of time and effort. Digital wallets offer both advantages and downsides. For example, they may be hacked by anybody, and passwords might be misplaced, leading in losses. Accessing the digital wallet necessitates a connection to an electronic device for interactions, which is not accessible to everyone. A data connection is also necessary, which is not always feasible for low-income individuals. Thus, while a digital wallet is something that everybody can use and that makes life simpler, it cannot always be so advantageous because it has some limits. Since the demonetization, the use of e-wallets has skyrocketed as individuals transition to a cashless economy, allowing them to utilize this gadget or service anywhere, at any time. E-wallets are excelling in financial services because they eliminate the need for individuals to visit banks for transactions.

Paytm

Paytm, or "Pay via Mobile," was founded in 2010 by One 97 Communications as a prepaid mobile & DTH recharge company. It gradually entered e-commerce business in 2014, & in 2015, it included bus tickets to its application. Paytm currently provides a variety of items ranging from basic cellphone recharges to purchasing things, allowing clients to obtain everything in one spot. As a result, it has evolved into both a payment platform & a marketplace over time. The current study is based on primary & secondary data, which was gathered through a variety of random sampling, books, business magazines, journals, newspapers, research studies, internet, web sites, & so on., This will highlight users' usage of digital wallets, with a focus on Paytm in the Meerut region. Paytm is becoming more popular in today's corporate sector, as are mobile phones. Individuals use mobile devices to access numerous capabilities wherever they are and whenever they need them. Moreover, paytm is playing an important role by allowing customers to make online payments. Paytm has also provided ability of recharging & purchasing from anywhere & at any time by utilizing a secure online wallet known as paytm cash.

Objective of study

1. To have an insight into the concept of Paytm.
2. To understand the basic features of Digital payment system especially with Paytm.
3. To identify consumer adoption of digital payment with special reference to Paytm.

Review of Literature

In a study work, Bosker, B. (2011) critically highlighted the contours of the privacy risks associated with the use of digital wallet technology. The study concentrated on Google's future digital wallet. This would allow Google to obtain much more personal information about its customers than it now does "through online" services. Now, Google would collect data on a person's point-of-sale purchase decisions & utilize that data to construct its advertising activities.

According to Abhay Upadhyay (2012), the difficulties of payment transactions were previously underestimated in electronic commerce. Thus far, payment mechanisms in traditional companies have dominated transactions conducted over the internet and smart phones. Yet, with the growth of e-commerce, traditional business models are gradually reaching their limits. E-wallets are also a simple, user-friendly, & secure worldwide payment mechanism. This is a versatile "personal banking system" with a variety of payout & pay-in possibilities. In this case, I -Payout employs cutting-edge security methods to assure E-wallet security.

Farah Diba Abrantes Braga, Giuliana Isabella, and José Afonso Mazzon (2013) affirmed in their study that "Digital Wallet" as a payment option is becoming a trend in the economy. Based on earlier research, it demonstrated how payment types influenced consumer purchasing behavior. Yet, they had only evaluated cash and credit cards, not digital money. The researchers demonstrated how the integration of several structures related to payment methods in their study. They also looked at how they affected customer behavior. They claimed that digital money affected customer behavior in the same way as debit cards did. Eventually, the researchers submitted 14 suggestions about digital wallet payments in their article.

Gurpreet Singh Sambhy (2014) did research on "Mobile Payment Services" in India and indicated that electronic payment systems had been introduced, accepted, & widely used in information technology & payment systems. Mobile payment systems and their accompanying services were launched by payment systems. Mobile payment systems involve a variety of stakeholders, including telecom carriers, banks, shops, and customers. In a growing country like India, mobile payment systems have grown rapidly in terms of adoption and implementation. He emphasized that mobile payment systems need to evolve in order to deliver effective and efficient customization.

Ambarish Salodkar, Karan Morey, and Monali Shirbhate et al. (2015) performed research on implementation, benefits, & future scope of electronic wallets. They defined Digital Wallets as a virtual or cashless service provider that may replace actual currency transactions. The author's work focuses on delivering a novel manner of shopping and purchasing goods without the necessity of physical transactions. Customers should be able to conduct secure transactions that are rapid, effective, & efficient with the touch of a button. Yet, it has been discovered that "Security" remains the key issue for the majority of clients. They advised that customers develop a unique code for transactions

in order to use this Digital payment wallets service. This code will grant users access to their accounts.

Amal Nair, Manisha Dahiya, Naman Gupta, Rachna Yadav, and Richa Mehta (2016) conducted a study on "Digital Wallets" education. They said that digital wallets are platforms that store users' payment information & passwords, enable them to perform electronic transactions, & simplify their lives. They also noted the many advantages of digital wallets. Among these advantages include the ability to transfer money, pay bills, and use services such as cab services. Apart from the simplicity of access & usage, it is highly beneficial for the vast unorganized sector where cash is seen as the most acceptable form of payment. When it comes to the usage of digital wallets, various people from diverse backgrounds react differently. As a result, it is critical for all digital wallet firms to segment their consumer base based on who wants to use and respond to the wallet. After witnessing so many recent scams and incidents involving cash transactions, many individuals believe that this will be the most popular way of financial transaction in the future.

Emrah Oney et al. (2017) assessed the factors of e-Payment systems from perspective of customers. The study developed a conceptual model to examine drivers of e-payment system adoption, as well as influence of perceived security and trust. Structural equation modeling was used to evaluate 299 respondents for this study. Furthermore, the data show that "perceived security" and "trust" both have a considerable impact on EPS use. Lastly, this study discovered that technological protection & prior experience were two predictors of customer perceived security & trust.

M. Naranjo-Zolotov, T. Oliveira, and S. Casteleyn et al. (2019) investigate the impact of those aspects that influence the user's desire to embrace and recommend e-participation using the UTAUT model and empowerment theory. An electronic survey was used to obtain data from 210 e-participation users. Structural Equation Modeling is used to build a model that predicts customer intent to use. According to the findings, physiological empowerment has a direct and positive impact on consumer intention, as well as influences to encourage e-participation. The model also reveals that the most influential and strongest determinants of consumer intention are enabling circumstances and performance anticipation. Consumer inclination to utilize e-participation was unrelated to social influence or effort expectation. The study adds to understanding consumer perceptions of empowerment, which might impact the intention to use the e-participation system in the future by employing unique theoretical models.

According to Shinki Katyayani Pandey et al. (2022), digital payments in India increased by 26.2 percent in volume during 2020-21, following a 44.2 percent increase the previous year. Finally, during the COVID-19 epidemic, people were concerned about health rules and feared cash transactions, which caused them to transfer to this method, resulting in an increase in use of various digital payment systems.

Methodology

The present research includes exploratory research and descriptive research. This study is based on infinite universe sample and is represented by all the customers using digital wallet in Meerut region. Universe of the present study is service and business class people of the Meerut region. A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed in all four areas of Meerut district, with 325 being included in the research. 75 questionnaires could not be included in the study because they were not fully filled out. Consequently, the study included 325 samples. Primary data for the present study was collected through a structured questionnaire. In this study the most common survey methods are used online surveys, in-person interviews, mail-in surveys and mobile surveys. The google form questionnaire for the study is filled by people of Meerut region who are the users of digital wallets. Primary data for study was collected through 400 questionnaires filled with respondents. Secondary data includes published information from past research work, and which is important in guiding the path for present study.

Analysis

Data Analysis And Data Interpretations

In this study, hypotheses were assessed by calculating the likelihood that sample statistics could have been selected if the population parameter hypothesis was valid. The current research study's hypothesis was tested utilizing a variety of statistical methodologies, including SPSS.

Ho1: There is no significant difference b/w demographic profile of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Ha1: There is significant difference b/w demographic profile of respondents and factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Ho1g: There is no significant difference b/w the gender of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Ha1g: There is significant difference b/w the gender of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Table 1: Association Between Adoption & Gender

		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Adoption	Low	90	102	192
	Medium	55	69	124
	High	2	7	9
Total		147	178	325

The table above shows the relationship between respondents' gender and their level of Adoption about the digital wallets they use. There were 147 males and 178 females among those who responded. Among the male respondents, 90 (male) had little adoption of the digital wallet, 55 had medium knowledge, and the remaining three were highly aware.

Whereas 102 female respondents had poor understanding of the digital wallet, 69 had medium adoption, and the remaining 7 were highly aware. An examination of the replies received about the relationship between the respondents' adoption of digital wallets and their gender indicates that most of the respondents are females, and the association between the two variables (adoption and gender) is nearly identical. Except for the dispersion of high levels of adoption among female respondents, which appear to be proportionally higher than that of male respondents. However, while the proportion of female respondents is higher than that of male respondents used in this study, this apparent difference is insufficient to indicate that females are more aware of digital wallets than males. The analysis indicated that the link between adoption and gender is consistent with the gender distribution of respondents used in this study.

Table 2: Chi-Square test

	Value	DF	ASYMP. Sig. (2-Sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.487	2	0.038
Likelihood ratio	7.157	2	0.027
Linear-By-Linear association	3.075	1	0.081
N Of Valid cases	325		

The chi-square test has a Pearson Chi-Square of 6.487, as seen in the table below. The table's p-value is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), hence we reject the null hypothesis. Instead, it is expected that there is a significant disparity between gender and knowledge levels. Based on the findings, we may conclude that a correlation exists between gender and adoption level ($X^2 = 6.487, p = 0.038$).

Ho1a: There is no significant difference b/w the age of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Ha1a: There is difference b/w the age of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Table 3: Association Between Adoption & Age

		Age (Years)				Total
		Below 30	31-50	51-64	Above	
Adoption	Low	73	85	30	4	192
	Medium	36	64	24	0	124
	High	4	5	0	0	9
Total		113	154	54	4	325

The table above shows relationship b/w respondents' ages & their level of adoption of digital wallets. It has been noticed that among the respondents chosen for the purposes of this study, 113 are under age of 30, 154 are b/w the ages of 31 & 50, 54 are b/w the ages of 51 and 64, & the remaining 4 are older than 64 years. Among respondents under the age of 30: 73 had little knowledge of digital wallets, 36 had medium consciousness, and the remaining 4 were very aware. Among participants aged 31 to 50, 85 had little adoption of digital wallets, 64 had intermediate adoption, and the remaining 5 were very aware. Among respondents aged 51 to 64 years, 30 had little knowledge of the digital wallet, 24 had medium adoption, and none were very aware of it. Whereas all respondents aged 65 and up showed a poor level of understanding of digital wallets.

An analysis of the responses collected regarding the relationship between the understanding of digital wallet and age group of respondents reveals that majority of individuals belong to category of young and developed age group, with a middle level of adoption with regard to the digital wallet, followed by those who are in younger age group, i.e. those under the age of 30 years; while those over the age of 65 years have only a low level of adoption regarding the digital wallet. The dispersion of the responses collected reveals that there is a significant correlation b/w adoption and respondents age, which is supported by practicality, as respondents aged 31-50 years are the ones who make the most use of digital wallets for their purposes, proving the accuracy of the data used in this study.

Table 4: Chi-Square Test

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-Sided)
Pearson chi-Square	15.726	2	0.016
Likelihood Ratio	21.606	2	0.002
Linear-By-Linear Association	.267	1	0.066
N. Of valid Cases	325		

According to the table below, the Pearson Chi-Square for the Chi-Square test is 15.726. The table's p-value is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), hence we reject the null hypothesis. Rather, it is perceived as a significant age and knowledge disparity. Based on the findings, we may conclude that a correlation exists between age and adoption level ($X^2 = 15.726, p = 0.015$).

Ho1q: There is no significant difference b/w qualification of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Ha1q: There is significant difference b/w the qualification of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Table 5: Association Between Adoption & Qualification

		Qualification				Total
		Doctorate	Professional	Graduate	Higher Secondary	
Adoption	Low	41	64	61	26	192
	Medium	22	60	32	10	124
	High	1	4	2	2	9
Total		64	128	95	38	325

The above table shows relationship b/w respondents' qualifications & their level of adoption about digital wallets. It has been noticed that among the respondents chosen for the objectives of this study, 64 are qualified with doctorates, 128 are professionally qualified, 95 are qualified graduates, and the remaining 38 have higher secondary degrees. Among those who participated with doctorates, 41 had little understanding of the digital wallet, 22 had medium understanding, and the remaining two were highly aware. Among the experienced respondents, 64 had little understanding of the digital wallet, 60 had medium adoption, and the remaining 4 were highly aware. Among those interviewed with graduate degrees, 61 had little knowledge of the digital wallet, 32 had medium adoption, and the remaining 2 were well aware of it. Among those with a higher intermediate qualification, 26 had little adoption of the digital wallet, 10 had medium understanding, and the remaining two were very aware.

An analysis of the answers that were collected in regard to the relationship between the knowledge of digital wallet and the educational backgrounds of respondents reveals that majority of competently competent respondents carry better level of adoption with regard to the digital wallet as contrasted with the participants with other levels of qualifications, following those who are qualified students; while those with additional secondary credentials carry compared. The dispersion of the recorded responses reveals that there is an intense connection between participant consciousness and qualification, which is further supported by the actual needs of the respondents based on their qualifications, which indicate that individuals use digital wallets the most, followed by graduate candidates. Thus, the integrity of the outcome is confirmed.

Table 6: Chi-Square test

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig.(2-Sided)
Pearson chi-Square	17.233	2	0.007
Likelihood ratio	17.445	2	0.007
Linear-By-Linear Association	2.383	1	0.024
N Of Valid cases	328		

The following table shows that the Pearson Chi-Square in Chi-Square test is 17.233. The p-value in the table is smaller than significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), hence we reject null hypothesis. Rather, it is understood as a considerable gap between the qualifying factor and the comprehension level. Based on results, we can state that there is an association that was found between qualification and adoption level ($X^2 = 17.233, p = 0.008$).

Ho1o: There is no significant difference b/w the occupation of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Ha1o: There is significant difference b/w the occupation of respondents & factors influencing adoption of digital wallets.

Table 7: Association Between Adoption & Occupation

		Occupation		Total
		Employee/Job Holder/Job Seeker	Business/Self Employed	
Adoption	Low	94	98	192
	Medium	69	55	124
	High	6	3	9
Total		169	156	649

The table above shows relationship b/w respondents' occupations & their level of adoption of digital wallets. It has been noticed that among the respondents chosen for the purpose of this study, 169 respondents are employees/job holders/job seekers, while the remaining 156 respondents run their own businesses or are self-employed. Among the respondents who are employees/job holders/job seekers, 94 had little adoption of the digital wallet, 69 had medium adoption, and the remaining 6 were highly aware. Among participants who work in business or are self-employed, 98 had no knowledge of digital wallets, 55 had medium understanding, and the remaining 3 had high knowledge. An analysis of data collected on relationship b/w digital wallet consciousness & respondents' occupations reveals that most respondents with employment as their occupation have a higher level of adoption about digital wallets than those with business or self-employment as their occupation.

Table 8: Chi-Square test

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-Sided)
Pearsonchi-Square	5.537 ^a	2	0.064
Likelihoodratio	5.663	2	0.058
Linear-By-Linear Association	4.928	1	0.025
N Of Validcases	325		

The following table shows that the Pearson Chi-Square test is 5.537. The p-value in the table exceeds significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), hence we accept null hypothesis. Rather, it is believed that there is no substantial relationship between the job component and consciousness level. Based on results, we can state that there is no association b/w occupation & adoption level ($X^2 = 5.537, p = 0.063$).

Table 9: Association Between Adoption & Income

		Income				Total
		Below 200000	Between 200000 - 600000	Between 600000 - 1200000	Above 1200000	
Adoption	Low	43	65	58	26	192
	Medium	14	45	47	18	124
	High	2	1	4	2	9
Total		59	111	109	46	325

The above table shows the relationship amongst respondents' income and their level of adoption about digital wallets. It has been observed that of the total 325 people taken for the purpose of this study, 59 are in the income bracket of less than 200000, 111 are in the income brackets of 200000-600000, 109 are in the income bracket of 600000-1200000, and the remaining 46 respondents have an income of more than 1200000. Among participants with an income of less than \$200,000, 43 had little adoption of digital wallets, 14 had medium understanding, and the remaining four were very aware. Among respondents with incomes ranging from \$200,000 to \$600,000, 65 had little adoption of digital wallets, 45 had medium adoption, and the remaining 1 were very aware. Among the respondents with incomes ranging from 600000 to 1200000, 58 had poor adoption of digital wallets, 47 had medium adoption, and the remaining 4 were very aware. Among respondents with an income of more than 1200000, 26 had little adoption of digital wallets, 18 had medium adoption, and the remaining 2 were very aware.

An analysis of the responses collected in relation to the relationship between respondents' income and their level of adoption of digital wallets reveals that the majority of respondents with incomes ranging from Rs 60000 to 1200000 and employment as their occupation has a higher level of adoption of digital wallets than those with incomes less than 200000. This is backed by the fact that people in this income group frequently use digital services for formal payments because such gateways are commonly used by their companies. This demonstrates the validity of the finding.

Table 10: Chi-Squaretest

	VALUE	DF	ASYMP. SIG. (2-SIDED)
PEARSONCHI-SQUARE	21.516	2	0.001
LIKELIHOODRATIO	22.888	2	0.001
LINEAR-BY-LINEAR ASSOCIATION	10.824	1	0.001
N OF VALIDCASES	325		

The following table shows that the Pearson Chi-Square test is 21.516. The p-value in the table is smaller than significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), hence we reject null hypothesis. Rather, it is regarded as a big gap between income and education level. Based on results, we can state that there is an association that was found between income and adoption level ($X^2 > = 21.516, p = 0.001$).

Conclusion

The results of this hypothesis indicated that when demographic variable (age, gender, income occupation and qualification) were tested with independent variable (usage, preference, risk and reason) conclusion derived were mixed i.e. at some point null hypothesis was accepted and at some point, alternate hypothesis was accepted. Only in the case of gender along with independent variable null hypothesis was accepted while in the case of age, qualification, income and occupation alternate hypothesis was accepted. Demographic variables and factors influencing adoption of digital wallet have been analyzed. The results showed that gender and factors influencing adoption of digital wallets (usage, preference, reason and risk) had no significant difference. Next variable age and occupation along with preference, risk, reason and usage resulted in a significant relation. While in case of qualification only preference and risk had a significant impact, rest two factors, i.e. usage and reason, had no significant impact. Income had a significant impact when analyzed with usage, reason and risk, on the other hand no significant found in preference.

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